

ISic0481

I.Sicily inscription 0481

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Selinuntiae

Place of origin (modern)

Sciacca

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491706

EDCS 21900541

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7200 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Una nuova attestazione del cursus publicus dalla Sicilia tardoantica. In Demougin, S., Navarro Caballero, M.(eds.), *Se déplacer dans l'Empire romain : approches épigraphiques: XVIIIe rencontre franco-italienne*

d'épigraphie du monde romain, Bordeaux 7-8 octobre 2011. Bordeaux. pp. 123-133. At 124

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